

PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES

SOME DATA CONCERNING THE USE OF SARTANS IN PRACTICAL MEDICINE OF THE REPUBLIC OF BELARUS

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Abstract

Cardiovascular diseases (CVD) are one of the main causes of disability and mortality of the adult population in the world. Arterial hypertension (AH) occupies a leading position among CVD in terms of the number of patients. Therefore, the choice of adequate therapy for arterial hypertension is of paramount importance. The article discusses the use of angiotensin II receptor blockers (ARBs or sartans) in practical medicine of the Republic of Belarus.

Keywords: cardiovascular diseases, arterial hypertension, chronic heart failure, angiotensin II receptor blockers (ARBs).

Introduction. Cardiovascular diseases, being one of the main causes of disability in the Republic of Belarus, occupy one of the leading places in the structure of disability and mortality of the adult population.

It is important that the European Bureau of the World Health Organization (WHO Regional Office for Europe, 2017) classifies Belarus as a country with an extremely high risk of cardiovascular diseases. The risk of heart attack in our country is 5 times higher than in France.

The high prevalence of cardiovascular diseases (CVD) is closely related to lifestyle characteristics and various risk factors. Modification of risk factors leads to a decrease in cardiovascular mortality and morbidity, especially in high-risk patients [7, p. 6].

Arterial hypertension is one of the main risk factors for the development of CVD. Mortality from coronary heart disease and stroke increases linearly with an increase in systolic blood pressure up to more than 115 mmHg and diastolic blood pressure up to more than 75 mmHg [8, P. 14]

Currently, one billion people in the world suffer from arterial hypertension (AH). Arterial hypertension is an important risk factor for the development of cardiovascular complications and due to its widespread occurrence AH makes a significant contribution (from 35 to 45%) to cardiovascular morbidity and mortality [8, p.15].

According to the STEPS 2020 study in the Republic of Belarus, the situation with arterial hypertension is quite serious: 9.1% of residents of Brest region claim that they have never had their blood pressure measured, in Minsk and in Grodno region there are only 1.0% of them. In Brest region 79.0% of residents suffering from

hypertension (the largest share in the country) do not take prescribed medications against high blood pressure. The lowest level of such patients is in Minsk – the capital city of the country (50.5%) [9]. At the same time, on average, 28.5% of the adult population was diagnosed with hypertension in the Republic of Belarus. The COVID-19 pandemic has shown that the greatest risk of mortality from coronavirus is observed in people with certain CVD and their risk factors.

In such a situation, one of the important points in the treatment of hypertension is the selection of adequate treatment. Over the past decade, the first-line drugs for the treatment of hypertension are angiotensin II receptor blockers (ARBs, sartans). Specialists consider ARBs (sartans) not only as a means for the treatment of hypertension, but also as promising drugs for the prevention of a number of cardiovascular complications, the treatment of chronic heart failure and kidney diseases [10]. ARBs are considered as the drugs of choice for the treatment of arterial hypertension (AH), concomitant metabolic syndrome, left ventricular hypertrophy and microalbuminuria /proteinuria of any origin, chronic heart failure (CHF) and ACE intolerance.

According to studies conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic in China and the USA, the use of ARBs for the treatment of patients with arterial hypertension (AH) can not only reduce blood pressure, but also has a protective effect in viral lung damage – both by suppressing the synthesis of angiotensin II and by increasing the expression of APF2 – I contribute to the reduction of lung fibrosis [1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6].

The purpose of this study is to assess the breadth of the use of ARBs in the treatment of CVD in practical medicine in the Republic using a survey of physicians.

Materials and methods. The survey of physicians was conducted using the original questionnaire. The survey was conducted on the Internet using the Google forms service. Inclusion criteria was an informed consent. The results were processed using non-parametric statistics methods using the Google forms analysis package.

The study involved 40 respondents aged 29 to 61 years. Of these, cardiologists made up 20%, general practitioners (GPS) – 25%, therapists – 55%.

Results. The drugs of the ARB group have a serious evidence base. For example, as a result of blind randomized studies (CASE-J (Candesartan Antihypertensive Survival Evaluation in Japan), CATCH (Candesartan Assessment in the Treatment of Cardiac Hypertrophy), it was proved that in patients with left ventricular hypertrophy (LVH), candesartan led to a significantly pronounced decrease in left ventricular (LV) myocardial mass. In addition, the number of new cases of diabetes mellitus (DM) was significantly lower among patients taking candesartan [11]. With prolonged use of ARBs, the renal plasma flow increases without significantly affecting the glomerular filtration rate (GFR), and the excretion of albumins in urine in patients with hypertension with diabetic nephropathy decreases. ARBs have no adverse effect on purine metabolism, glucose metabolism and blood lipids [12]. The results of LIFE and SCOPE studies [13] have proven the effectiveness of ARBs in preventing strokes. The results of the VALUE study (2004), the largest study to date devoted to evaluating the effectiveness of valsartan therapy, proved the ability of this drug to prevent atrial fibrillation. Moreover, Valsartan is the only drug from the ARB group that is included in the National Recommendations for the Diagnosis and Treatment of acute myocardial infarction (AMI) with an increase in the ST segment on the ECG.

As a result of the survey, it was found out that the most commonly used ARBs in practical medicine are losartan (commercial names: Sental, Zartan, Lorista, Co-Sental, Prezartan N, Lozar N, Lortenza, etc.) and valsartan (commercial names: Valsacor, Sartval, etc.). At the same time, 90% of the surveyed specialists prescribe losartan from time to time to their patients with CVD, and another 5% prefer this particular drug in the treatment of hypertension.

As for valsartan, this drug is even more popular with doctors. Thus, 95% of respondents prefer to prescribe it, while pointing out the need to take into account the risks in elderly patients, as well as during pregnancy. Considering that valsartan gives good results when used in combination therapy of CVD, almost all survey participants (95%) use valsartan combination drugs. The most popular are Valsacor H (valsartan + hydrochlorothiazide), Valsartan Plus (valsartan + hydrochlorothiazide) and Valodip (amlodipine + valsartan). These medicines are prescribed by 65% of the survey participants. 60% of respondents use Co-Valodip in the treatment of hypertension and CHF

– a complex drug consisting of three components: amlodipine, valsartan, hydrochlorothiazide. The only drug that increases the left ventricular ejection fraction is Uperio, which is a combination of valsartan with sacubitril. However, only 25% of respondents use this drug in their practice. The main reason for refusing to use this drug (38.3% of those who do not prescribe Uperio) is the high cost of the drug, the absence of the main preferential drugs in the list (17%), as well as ignorance of this drug (44.7%).

Quite often, survey participants use candesartan (commercial names: Candesartan-NAN, Kanvers, Kasark, Kanvers plus). At the same time, 70% of respondents prescribe it from time to time, 15% prescribe this drug at the request of patients, 5% know it, but do not prescribe it, and 10% of the surveyed specialists are not familiar with this drug. It should be noted that 35% of the survey participants use candesartan in case of patients' intolerance to ACE inhibitors. The interviewed specialists note that they do not use this drug in case of pregnancy of patients. It is also used with caution in elderly patients and in patients with severe renal insufficiency.

One of the newest drugs from the sartan group is Edarbi (azilsartan medoxomil). As a result of numerous studies, including a study conducted by the Federal State Budgetary Institution "National Medical Research Center of Cardiology" of the Ministry of Health of the Russian Federation, it was found that against the background of Edarbi® therapy, 82% of patients with grade 1-2 hypertension and metabolic syndrome reached the target blood pressure level. At the same time, the diastolic function of the left ventricle significantly improved in 56% of patients, which was accompanied by a decrease in the stiffness of the main arteries and an improvement in metabolic control [14]. However, during the study it was found out that 45% of the surveyed doctors do not know this drug, another 25% have heard about it, but do not prescribe it because of poor knowledge of its characteristics. At the same time, they note the high cost of this drug as one of the reasons for not assigning Edarbi (or Edarbi-clo). This drug is used from time to time in the treatment of hypertension and CHF by 25% of respondents, and 5% of specialists note that azilsartan is the drug of choice for refractory hypertension.

Answering questions about irbesartan (commercial names: Rebtazar, Irbesartan), 30% of respondents noted that they did not know this drug, and another 30% noted that they had heard about it, but did not use it, because they did not know this drug well. At the same time, the results of many randomized clinical trials consistently show that the frequency of side effects when using this drug, even in high dosages, is extremely low and comparable to placebo [15]. It is important to note a significant reduction in the risk of diabetic nephropathy regardless of the antihypertensive effect of the drug. The results of the IRMA 2 study also revealed a pronounced nephroprotective effect with a significant reduction in the risk of developing proteinuria when taking irbesartan.

The results of the study indicate that 60% of respondents do not know about such a representative of

the BRA group as olmesartan (commercial name: Olmecor). Only 20% of the survey participants prescribe this drug from time to time, and 15% know it, but do not use it due to insufficient information about the advantages and disadvantages of this drug.

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